

TRANSLATIONS, RE-INVENTION, AND CONSTRUCTION OF PERSIAN HISTORIES DURING THE SECOND HALF OF THE 18TH CENTURY

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Abstract

The genesis of the Persian language in South Asia is seen back in the early Medieval period. It developed as a language of influence during the medieval period and reached its zenith under the Mughal empire. It was the Mughal courtly culture that pushed and prevailed it as the main language-Franca of South Asia during the 17th century A.D. However, by the beginning of the eighteenth century, the destiny of the Persian language and literature were to drastically change in the Indian sub-continent. This was due to a transnational phase for Indian socio-politics and literary culture, which began with the downfall of the Mughal Empire on the one hand and the rise of the East India Company on the other. During this phase, the Persian language was gradually marginalized and started fading its color as a language of influence and authority. Hindustani (later Urdu and Hindi) and English were combinedly pushing it out and replacing it selves. In this critical time, East India company reimagined itself as a political re-constructer of Mughal province. This political transformation led the Persian language into a new phase. British colonialists had desires to be the real master of India. While India having a diverse culture, castes, and religions, there was no better option, other than the Persian literary sources, to understand it. British administrators, soldiers, engineers, linguists, politicians, and writers used these Persian texts to the fullest to understand the core of Indian politics and the past. They also played the role of patron to Indian writers and authors. This new literary class, generally known as Munshis, gave birth to a new stage of history writings under new patronship. In the second half of eighteenth the century, officials and scholars of East India company multiplied their efforts to associate themselves with the study, translations, and production of new Persian histories. This emerged into a new shift in the core of historical narration as well as the audience of Persian historical traditions.

Keywords: Historiography; Persian; Eighteenth century; political transformation; East India company.

Introduction:

Historiography is the scientific study of historical writings. It deals with the evolution and different dimension of historical narratives over time. It also involves the study of the use of methodology, literary tool, and various source materials for the construction and reconstruction of history by the historian. The Indo-Persian tradition of chronicle writing, or the *Tarikh* tradition, had its roots in traditions of Arab historiography and then, subsequently, Persian historiography. The origin of Indo-Persian historiography is usually traced back to the advent of Islam in South Asia. It emerged as an Arabic-Perso tradition of history writings under the influence of Arab historians. By the Eleventh Century, the Turks emerged as a new dominant race and they replaced Arabs in every aspect of life. From here, Persian emerged as a new language of influence. During the early Medieval period, authors like Bal'amī, Fidousi, 'Abdul Zuhak Gardezi, and Abul Fazl Baihāqi led down a magnificent foundation of Persian history writings. They were followed by Al Baruni, Zia ud din Barni, and several other noted historians, under the ages of the Delhi sultanate. But the real peak of production of the

Persian histories came under the Mughal empire. Abul Fazl, Abdul Qadir Badā'ūnī, Abdul Hamīd Lahori, etc, and even the historical works of emperor Jahangir himself witnessed the climax of Persian history writings during the Mughal court. Persian thus emerged as the “language of the king, royal household, and the high Mughal Elite”.ⁱ Muzaffar Alam's study of the Mughal pursuit of Persian emphasizes the function of this language as a tool of administration, but perhaps, even more importantly, its ability to contribute to the creation of political culture, “arching over diverse Indian religious and cultural identities, Persian in the existing circumstances promised to be the appropriate vehicle to communicate and sustain such an ideal”.ⁱⁱ After the disintegration of the Mughal empire as a central authority, various regional power emerged. Again, under these kingdoms, Persian histories saw a reasonable production.

Everything was in the favor of Indo-Persian historiography up to the end of the seventh century A.D. But, from the 18th century onward the bright color of the Persian language started fading away. This was the result of the decline of the Mughal empire after the death of the last great ruler, Aurangzeb, in 1707. AD. The political turmoil led to the disintegration of every aspect of the Indian sub-continent. It was not just a political transformation, but an overall transformation, including the social, cultural, and economic sphere.

The second half of the 18th century was a transitional phase for Indian politics. It was a time of Fall and Rise, of two major empires, Mughals and British respectively. As the Mughal empire Persian was also in its declining phase. It was the time when the British mercantile company entirely transformed its interests and activities into a complete imperial project. Along with conquering India for Imperial purposes, the British left no stone unturned to shape their own national consciousness in the Indian subcontinent. It was through the translation, reinvention, and reconstruction of Indian literary objects that the British tried to forge a new national identity. Bernard Cohn has observed that “the intensified production of colonial knowledge, in the late 18th century, had two primary goals or effects: to transform knowledge itself, and in particular, Indian scholars into an instrument of colonial rule”.ⁱⁱⁱ This political transformation initiated an all-new phase of Persian language and literature. British intelligentsia involved into a “massive and institutionalized study of Persian literary heritage”. History writings were one of the most produced literary components of this period. It was the time when a new generation of authors came into the focus. There were three main characteristics of history writings under this new project of colonialism. First, translation of all the important medieval histories into Urdu and English, to make them more accessible for the British working class. Second, the production of new historical works according to their own wills and wishes. And the Third is the formation of a new social class of historians/ linguists, loyal to the British rule, generally known as “*Munshis*” of the Raj.

Translations and Re-invention of Persian Historical Writings:

The victory at Plassey in 1757 A.D, raised the morale of the East India Company to become the main contender of the ruler of India. After getting control over the revenue of Bengal, the company got an opportunity to organize a strong and smart army to conquer the rest of India. in 1764 at Buxar, the company gave another blow to the combined force of three main power of the time. As Peter Marshal noted in his study of Bengal, “the year 1765 when the east India company became the Emperor’ Diwan, has come to be seen as the dividing line between Mughal and British Bengal”.^{iv} This fast-growing richness of the company enables its all-around development and prestige. In 1767, Benjamin Kennecott, a renowned Hebrew scholar suggested in a proposal to set up a post of the professorship of Persian language at the University of Oxford. According to him, “the great and rich possessions of

East India Company in that part of the world make it of the utmost consequence to them to have a person in their service well instructed in the Persian language”.^v

As a result, Calcutta became the main hub for the production of the new colonial historical works. William Jones (1746-1794) compiled an important work, *A Grammar of the Persian Language*, which was printed in 1771 A.D. In 1784 A.D, “Asiatic Society” was established at Calcutta under the leadership of William Jones. This was a landmark for the growth and encouragement of Oriental studies in India. It consolidated in the establishment of Fort William College at Calcutta, in 1800. According to Kapil Raj, Fort William was “the first of a series of institutions in which these different knowledge traditions and their corresponding skills were brought together, standardized, and rendered teachable”.^{vi} The Asiatic Society of Bengal extended useful services to the cause of oriental learning and literature. The publication of rare and valuable oriental texts and their translations into English were the most important. British administrators were alien to the Persians; therefore, they failed to get direct access to the sources of knowledge of the subcontinent. As a result, they generally relied on the established educated class, linked with the Mughal court, individuals, or employed in any one of the provincial kingdoms. But this educated class was now under the influence of East India Company. Many members of the Persian literary community, linked with typical Persian literary courts of South Asia, navigated themselves to the new British Colonial Administration. They also played the role of interpreter, translator, and informer as well. “The knowledge of the country was drawn largely from Indian sources and supplied by Indian Agents”.^{vii} Most of the time they mentioned the values and glory of previous Persian language courts of the medieval period while translating historical sources. At the same time, they highlighted the cultural and political differences between indigenous rule and company affairs. Most of these historians were not exclusively authors but often served in administration as judges, advisors, ministers, and bureaucrats as well. The influence of this bi-tasking, didactic nature, and a touch of the genre of advice literature, witnessed clearly in their writings. These native colonial scholars produced a colonial Persian historiographical tradition during the second half of the 18th century in India. According to Kumkum Chatterjee, “most colonialist accounts connected the decline of the Mughal empire with the rise of the English East India Company. Another theme that runs through the narratives of the English authors and their reflections on the Mughal Empire is that of Oriental or Asiatic despotism”. She primarily focused on Persian-based Orientalists like, Alexander Dow, Francis Gladwin, and William Kirkpatrick and their endeavors. She concludes, “these scholars were familiar with Persian literature including accounts of past rulers and their modes of governance and that their own views on Mughal governance were derived directly from the authors of Persian accounts”.^{viii} For example, Alexander Dow's *History of Hindustan* (1770) of which the first and second volumes were supposed to be a direct translation of Firishta's history, and the same is the case with, *History of India as Told by Its Own Historians*, of H. M. Elliott and J. Dowson (1867-1877).

Salim ul Allah Munshi (fl.1769), was one of the earliest colonial historians. He composed *Tarikh-i-Banglah*, one of the crucial histories of the second half of the 18th century, under the commission of Henry Vansittart, high-level British administrator and the governor of Fort William from 1760-1764. *Tarikh-i-Bnaglah* is a detailed work of contemporary events in Bengal from 1695 to 1756. It Reveals one of the “characteristic literary elements of colonial historiographical tradition”. The author provides a detailed survey of the dynastic succession of Bengal. He conveys this useful information to the British administration. This information was primarily for understanding the process of ruling and the succeeding, “who ruled and how ruled, and who and how succeeded to the rule”. This reorientation of the narrative and intent to strict neutral and fact-finding are the signs of modern historiography.

The translation of useful Persian historical sources into English was one another most dominated

colonial project in the 18th century.^{ix} *Tarikh-i-Bangalah* was translated into English by Francis Gladwin in 1788. He was a noted translator of Persian. Later, in 1801 he joined Fort William college as the first professor of Persian. He translated some of the most important Persian texts, such as the *Ain-i-Akbari* and *The history of Hindustan During the reign of Jahangir, Shahjahan, and Aurangzeb*, (1788) were published at an official level. Later was partly translation and partly reinvention based on earlier Persian historical works. The translation of the first volume of *Ain-i-Akbari*, which was completed in 1783, was dedicated to Warren Hasting the first Governor-general of India.^x Similarly, Charles Stewart was an orientalist and an Assistant professor of Persian at Fort William College (1801-1806), who served as a translator of Persian texts into English under East India Company. Among his major projects, *The History of Bengal*, written from a study of Persian sources is most important.^{xi} In this work, “Stewart used fourteen Persian manuscripts, of which twelve were from Tipu Sultan's Library”.^{xii}

In the words of Michael Dodson, “translation made available legal cultural information for the administration and rule of the non-west”. In his opinion, “translation was a strategic means for representing otherness to primarily domestic British reading audiences”.^{xiii} A servant of the East India Company, Captain Jonathan Scott (1754-1829) who also worked as a personal translator to Warren Hastings, translated a Persian source into English, under the title, *The Memoirs of Eradut Khan* (1649-1716), who he described as a “nobleman of Hindostan” was published in London in 1786. A.D. The memoir contains some interesting and useful anecdotes about Aurangzeb and his successors Shah Alam and Jahandar Shah. It also provides crucial information about the causes of the “very precipitate decline of the Mogul Empire in India”.^{xiv} As Kumkum Chatterjee has indicated, “British accounts of the collapse of the Mughal empire depended heavily on Persian sources”. Thus, the histories of India written in English by the British authors were mainly based on Persian texts produced in India and their English translations.^{xv}

In most of the cases, the translation of Persian sources was done also to learn about the different useful aspects of Indian society. The study of ethnic groups of India was one of the most important among others. The history of one part of India was seen to be a useful and important source of learning and information for the rest of the country. Another work entitled *British India Analyzed: The Provincial and Revenue Establishments of Tippu Sultan and Mahomedan and British Conquerors of Hindustan* was printed in London in 1793 in three parts. Its one part was published in Calcutta in 1792, was entitled *The Mysorean Revenue Regulations*, and translated by Burish Crisp(1762-1811).^{xvi} In the preface of the book, it was stated that the Parisian copy of the regulations, from which this translation has been made, bears the original seal impressions of Tipu Sultan. The Persian source was in the possession of Colonel John Murray who acquired it during the Coimbatore campaign, and it was the “most accurate delineation of the modern Mahomedan government that has appeared”. The translator shared the difficulties he faced while translating this into English. he stated it was very unfortunate, that after a long search I have not been able to find a single person in Calcutta who could translate for him the Malabar dialects or explained provincial terms.^{xvii} Hence he had no way other than to explain the terms from context. These kinds of episodes describe the dependence of British translators on native literates for information about terms etc. Translated historical texts became more accessible to the servants of the company. Once a single copy manuscript could be transformed, after translation, into printed English texts and that could be circulated much more rapidly and widely with ease, throughout the country.^{xviii}

According to Ranajit Guha, “some of the very first and most important works on Indian history written from a British standpoint belong to the period the colonial Era, of the thirty years between the grant of

Diwani (1765) and Permanent Settlement (1793)”. He thinks that most of these works were content to take a relatively foreshortened view of the past going back no further than the thirteenth century and quite a few of these ranged widely over time from antiquity to the most recent past.^{xix} The East India Company in Bengal showed a great interest in gathering information about the past kingdoms. This urgency often found expression in exasperation and frustration with their Indian ‘informants’ who they believed, were withholding critically important information from them. Ranajit Guha characterizes this as a form of resistance to British rule.^{xx}

Construction of General Histories;

Siyar-al-Mutaakhirin; First Persian discourse upon English Politics in Bengal.

Most of the late 18th century works written in Persian under the commission of British authorities deal specifically with the Indian region of Bengal. The region where the British first enrooted themselves and then kicked off the conquest of whole India. Bengal was not only rich in its economic resources but its richness was visible by its cultural and literary contribution in India. It had produced several historians, writers, linguists, and other influential personalities up to the 18th century. Amongst all Ghulām Ḥussain Ṭabatabai (b.1727-1728) was one of the most prominent Persian historians and held an important office under the East India Company. His father and uncles served in the court of Aliverdi Khan (1676-1756), the Nawab of Bengal. He officially played an important role in establishing cordial relations between the Rohilla leader, Ḥāfīz Raḥmat Khān (1708-1774) and the East India Company.^{xxi} In the 1760’s he entered into the service of the East India Company and during the rule of Mir Qasim, the Nawab of Bengal between 1760-1763, he was the principal envoy to the British delegation in Calcutta. He was appointed as Revenue Collector of Chunagarh in 1774. Tabatabai completed his three volumes book, *Siyar-al-Mutaakhirin* (History of modern times), in 1781, and dedicated his work to the first governor-general of Bengal Warren Hastings. Ghulām Ḥusayn Ṭabāṭabā’ī was greatly influenced by Sujan Rai Bhandari’s Persian work, *Khulāṣat al-tavārīkh* (The compendium of histories), which was completed in 1696 as a landmark in the literary production of Aurangzeb’s period. The general introduction to the *Siyar al-Muta’akhhirīn* displays the latest pattern in historical consciousness that took shape in 18th-century Persian historiography. “Unlike general universal histories written in Persian begin with two mythic cosmogonies: Islamic (life of Adam, the progenitor of humankind, and his subsequent descendants of prophets leading up to the time of Muhammad) and Persian (the myth of origins of an ancient Persian model that begins with the life of Gayumarth and proceed through the history of Persian kings), Ghulām Ḥussain placed India in a singular linear narrative as a succession of dynasties who ruled a single unified region, India, through time”.^{xxii} Indian History begins with the ancient king Yudhiṣṭhira followed by other important Hindu kings up to Pṛthviraj Chauhān. Prithviraj was defeated by Mohammad Gauri. Thus, the Hindu rule was succeeded by Muslim rule and followed by the British. The above chronology is the most typical characteristic of colonial British historiography. The larger part of the *Siyar al-Mutaakhhirīn* deals with the events such as the death of Aurangzeb and the process of succession after his death. It treats in detail the political and military history of Bengal from the Nizamat of Murshidabad and the affairs of ‘Alīvardī Khān, the British victory at Plassey, Robert Clives’ diplomacy with Shāh Ālam II, Shujā’ al-Dawla’s capitulation to the British in Awadh, the events of Muhammad Shāh’s (1719-1748) reign, the Maratha encounter with Aḥmad Shāh Durrāni, the rulers of Mysore state, the death of Nawāb Mīr Qāsim, down to 1781. Another significant aspect of his *Siyar-al-Mutakhhirin* is that it has given a piece of good information about the English affairs up to the time of Warren Hastings. No other Persian historian dealt with this aspect of the political life of English.

The *Siyar-ul-Mutakhirin* was based on some early Persian historical works. Although Ghulam Hussain Tabatabai never makes this explicit. The author of the *Siyar* stated that he gathered the information for his book from ‘persons of eminent rank and credit’, who he also described as his ‘authorities.

Ghulam Hussain Tabatabai thinks that the real cause of Siraj's removal from power, which paved the way for a dramatic escalation in the power of the English East India Company in Bengal and then the British empire in India respectively, lay in the fact that “he lacked the qualities and virtues that good rulers must-have”. Ghulam Hussain Tabatabai portrayed him as “unwise and capricious, and worse”, who ignored and humiliated the nobility who had helped the previous nawab to rule wisely and well. What eventually led to Siraj's downfall, in his opinion, as a contemporary commentator, was that he gave prominence to certain undeserving people who gave him bad and unsound advice.^{xxiii}

He was also a critic of company policies. he has observed that The Company's lack of concern, or ‘affection’, for the people of their dominions in eastern India was regarded as a serious deficiency in its administration.^{xxiv} He thus categorically stated that the problems between ruler and ruled lay in a sea of differences comprised of divergent political values and cultural practices that had yet to be bridged.^{xxv} Ghulam Hussain Tabatabai condemned the Company for its seeming incapacity to understand the “noble principles on which certain institutions of indigenous government were based”.^{xxvi}

While considering the *Siyar-al-Mutaakhirin* as one of the most important works of the 18th century, we must highlight some drawbacks from which it suffers. First, the pro-Shia feeling of the author, second, hostility toward Nawab Siraj ud Daula, And third his pro-English Attitude.

Treatment of History by Ghulam Hussain Salim in *Riyaz-us-Salatin*

The study of Persian history writings during the second half of the 18th century become much interesting and exciting when we interacted with another masterpiece of history, *Riyaz-us-Salatin* of Ghulam Hussain Salim. Ghulam Hussain Salim, born in Zaidpur, Uttar Pradesh, and in his youth, migrated to Malda, Bengal. He held the office of Dak Munshi (post-master) under George Udny, who was in charge of an indigo concern in Malda in northern Bengal, and here he started writing the book *Riyaz-us-Salatin* in 1786 AD, at the request of the latter.^{xxvii} Completed in 1788 A.D, it covers the whole Muslim rule in Bengal, some lacunas are the exception, from the establishment of Delhi sultanate 1206 AD up to the battle of Plassey in 1757 AD. In his wide introduction, he begins with the geographical and topographical features and population followed by the origin of the people of Bengal, their living conditions, and a description of some important cities. And then he closed his introductory part with a brief overview of the reigns of Hindu kings who had ruled over Bengal before the conquest of the region by Bakhtiyar Khalji. The rest of the book he divided into four chapters. Ghulam Hussain Salim's main interest was in tracing the reigns of Muslim kings in Bengal—the earlier phase consisting of the rule of the ‘rais’ as he called them, being a sort of casual preamble to the main story. The succession of kings he described seems to have been similar to the list of pre Muslim Bengal kings were given in the *Ain-i-Akbari* by Abul Fazl.^{xxviii}

Maulavi Abdus Salam, the translator-cum-editor of the *Riyaz-us-Salatin* wrote that though Ghulam Husain Salim does not mention all the sources, he based on his *Riyaz-us-Salatin*. But it appears that he used Persian historiographical works such as *Tabaqat-i-Nasiri* of Minhaj-i-Siraj, *Tarikh-i-Firuzshahi* of Ziauddin Barani, and *Tarikh-i-Mubarak shahi* of Yahya bin Ahmad to write about the medieval Bengal. He could also probably consult the Afghan and Mughal histories, Abul Fazl's *Ain-i-Akbari* and *Akbarnamah*, Badauni's *Muntakhab-ut-Tawarikh*, and Nizamuddin Bakhshi's *Tabaqat-i-Akbari* and other important Mughal histories.^{xxix} As the Bengal under Nawab in concerned, Ghulam

Husain Salim consulted *Tarikh-i-Bangla* of Salim ul Allah Munshi and. Sayyid Ghulam Husain Tabatabai's *Siyar-ul-Mutaakhkherin* and other books written by his contemporaries were also available to him. He also admits that he had consulted a 'little book' and a book of Haji Muhammad Arif Qandahari both are unavailable for now. He also deciphered inscriptions attached to mosques and other monuments placed in famous cities of Bengal. These epigraphical pieces of evidence utilized by the author enhance the importance of his book. The book has been translated into English by Molvi Abdus Salam. But because of its lacunas in history narrations, modern historians would have found it difficult to reconstruct a correct framework of the history of Muslim rule in Bengal by using this book. He did not mention some Mughal subahdars, particular mention may be made of Shaista Khan whose glorious reign has not received due attention. Modern scholars express surprise that Shaista Khan's great achievement in Bengal, viz the conquest of Chittagong, has been lost sight by the author is unfortunate. Despite such omissions and drawbacks, the *Riyaz-us-Salatin* should be given credit for being the first indigenous work attempting a complete history of the Muslim rule in Bengal. That is why several modern Historians and scholars have accepted *Riyaz-us-Salatin* as a model and based his narratives on the same.

Purpose and Methodology

The precolonial Persian historiographical traditions generally covered the history of a particular dynasty. But it was not the case with new evolving historical consciousness under the colonial historiographical project which gradually began to conceptualize India as a singular historical subject. These eighteenth-century narratives perceived governmental ideals to be moral objectives that were not dependant on considerations of rigidly defined religious doctrine, or the values of particular ethnic or even dynastic groups. A common feature shared by the Regional history of Bengal studied here is that they gave central importance to the reigns of the autonomous Nawabs of Bengal, from Murshid Quli Khan to Nawab Sirajuddaula. Ghulam Hussain Khan Tabatabai located his narrative about developments in Bengal concerning major political events in the Mughal empire since the death of Aurangzeb in 1707. As Ghulam Hussain Tabatabai wrote, "his intention, in writing was...to furnish to some intelligent man the means of giving the public at some distant time hereafter, an idea of preceding reigns".^{xxx} Likewise, Ghulam Hussain Salim primarily focused on the reigns of the autonomous Nawabs of Bengal. For many of the authors of these historical writings, the purpose of composing these narratives about the reigns of past rulers, held immense value for the present because they served as educational and moral examples for the coming generations.^{xxxi} The historians of this period generally had independent and individual methods of collecting data and for the majority of historians, the only source for the collection of their data had only his pen, paper, and memory.^{xxxii}

The contemporary writers who saw the empire passing into the turmoil of internal rivalries did not hesitate to condemn the policies of the Emperors.^{xxxiii} For example, the well-known events in the history of early modern India, the removal of Nawab Sirajuddaula (1756–57) from power through a conspiracy. Most of the *Tarikh* writers under consideration here were contemporaries of Nawab Sirajuddaula, and they are unanimous in agreeing that the real cause of Siraj's removal from power lay in the fact that he lacked the qualities and virtues of a ruler.

The authors of early-modern India generally tried to establish their connection with the classical tradition of medieval Indo-Persian and Persian historiography. This deliberate endeavor was supposed to set an intellectual and cultural link with the classical-Persian tradition which had existed from the centuries. Allusions to personalities and events from Persian and Islamic history and cultural traditions also abounded in these manuscripts. Ghulam Hussain Salim compared his patron, an Englishman

named George Udny, to Hatim (an Arab prince of ancient times) and Naushirwan (an ancient Iranian king reputed in particular for his dispensation of justice).^{xxxiv} Salimullah Munshi, in his *Tarikh-i-Bangla*, called emperor Aurangzeb a 'second Jemshed'.

Conclusion:

In Conclusion, history writing in India and during the second half of the 18th century was the product of a transitional period. It was a complex and uncertain phase for the languages and ideas of writings. After the shrinking of Mughal central authority, Persian historical writings of India were produced under the regional courts. British colonial administrators have approached this literary heritage to translate and mould that knowledge for their own uses. Persian histories were used to understand India's past. A new literati class emerged as the munshis; this class played the role of the informants for the Raj. Apart from the translations of some important historical texts, there are several works were composed by the nobility and officials of the Mughal successor states. Most of these had been directly commissioned by the new English rulers of Bengal. Colonial scholars were interested in the Mughal history to learn about the Mughals and then replaced them as legitimate successors. They were much interested in its decline to learn "lessons from the past", and presumably apply these for their administration. The histories which were produced during the concerned period placed India in a singular linear narrative. The fact remains that the growth of the Persian literature, on the whole, was not hindered owing to the withdrawal of the imperial patronage and great hurdles that were placed before it during this period. As it continued to thrive on individual initiatives as it is evident from the mass of the literature produced in the language during this period in different branches of knowledge. The historian of this period rarely indulged in rhetoric or florid style of writing, lucidity, and simplicity was the main objective of their writings. Most of the historians are mainly contemporary to the events and incidents which they noted in their works.

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